

THE IMPORTANCE OF ADVOCACY IN ENHANCING REPRESENTATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This thesis explores the importance of advocacy and legal representation in enhancing civil litigation in Uzbekistan, especially within the context of the country's recent judicial reforms. It highlights the critical role of qualified legal assistance, the evolving demand for legal representation in civil cases, and the impact of these changes on protecting citizens' rights. The study emphasizes the need for improving the legal framework governing representation in court, driven by the increasing complexity of legal disputes and the growing number of civil cases in Uzbekistan's courts.

Key words: Advocate, advocacy, legal representation, judicial reforms, civil litigation, human rights, legal assistance, civil procedure, court representation, legal framework.

In recent years, the large-scale reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan under the leadership of the head of state on the path of modernizing the country and building a strong civil society are showing their effectiveness in all areas. This is especially noticeable in the judicial and legal sphere. In particular, the judicial system has been radically reformed, and the Constitution, along with many legislative acts and codes, has been adopted in new editions, taking into account democratic aspects.

A legal system based on the supremacy of human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests has been established. As a result of these reforms, the legal consciousness of our citizens has significantly changed, and judicial protection of their rights has become more prevalent. For the past years, as part of the action strategy for the five priority areas of the country's development for 2017-2021, approximately 300 laws and more than 4,000 resolutions of the President of the

Republic of Uzbekistan have been adopted, aimed at radically reforming all spheres of state and public life [1]. Systematic work has also been carried out to ensure human rights, strengthen the accountability and openness of government bodies, and increase the role of civil society institutions, the media, political activity of the population, and public associations.

Without stopping there, it should be especially noted that work is consistently and gradually continuing to deepen democratic reforms and effectively reform the judicial and legal system, which is an important strategic direction for the development of civil society. After all, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, No. PF-60 "On the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" provides for the establishment of effective judicial control over the activities of government bodies and officials, increasing the level of justice for citizens and business entities, and establishing actual equality and consent of the parties in litigation [2].

It is known that the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan not only secures the rights and freedoms of citizens but also guarantees their implementation. In particular, Article 54 of the Constitution stipulates that the provision of human rights and freedoms is the highest goal of the state and that the rights and freedoms of individuals are guaranteed by the state [3]. One of the most important duties of the legislators is to protect the rights and freedoms of individuals and guarantee their inviolability.

The importance of qualified legal assistance provided to citizens in realizing their right to legal protection is incomparable. Article 29 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees everyone the right to qualified legal assistance. In turn, qualified legal assistance is provided to citizens in various forms, including representation in court in civil cases. Representation in court in civil proceedings involves providing legal assistance to citizens and organizations, protecting their violated rights and legitimate interests.

Also, the participation of a representative in civil court cases helps clarify the relationship between the parties, increases the activity of participants in the process,

and serves to exercise public control over the civil process by social and civil structures and non-governmental organizations. Therefore, as the head of our state stated, we should pay special attention to the implementation of the legal norms adopted in recent years to expand the legal powers of public and civil structures and non-governmental organizations, and to the practical provision of human rights and freedoms, as well as improving the judicial system.

It should be noted that currently the importance of the institution of representation in court in civil proceedings is increasing. The institution of representation in court plays an important role in building a humane, legal, democratic state and a strong civil society. In this sense, in the conditions of democratization and renewal of society, modernization and reform of the country, increasing the status of this institution, increasing its powers and responsibilities, especially the task of providing qualified legal assistance, the need for further improvement of regulatory legal documents regulating the activities of the legal profession has arisen. This is the most common type of representation. In turn, the growing demand and need for qualified legal assistance in society are explained by an increase in the number of cases arising from various, new, and somewhat complex legal relationships in judicial practice.

For example, one of them is the participation of peasants in disputes related to various economic entities and societies, labor, housing, family, inheritance, and other issues. In addition, according to statistics, in 2019, 276,937 cases were considered by civil courts of first instance, in 2020 - 291,132, in 2021 - 518,087, in 2022 - 863,883, and in 2023 - 943,892 [4]. The regular increase in the number of civil cases in civil courts, as well as the high level of legislation regulating socio-economic relations, also indicates the relevance of a thorough study of the institution of representation in court.

Currently, the importance of the participation of persons with special knowledge in the field of jurisprudence as representatives in civil litigation is increasing. Especially in connection with the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 02/27/2024 O'RQ-915 “On the Provision of Legal Assistance at the Expense of

the State,” which includes some amendments and additions to regulatory documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The emergence of a serious change in the institution of (voluntary) representation under a contract in court requires effective legal regulation of related relations and the creation of a scientific basis for procedural mechanisms that ensure the implementation of existing norms in legislation. All this creates the need to develop a mechanism for the practical application of the provisions of Article 69 of the Civil Procedure Code on the institution of (voluntary) representation under a contract.

On the other hand, the transition of our country to a market economy, the constant improvement of our national legislation, and the increase in the number of cases arising from new and somewhat complicated legal relations in judicial practice create the need to consider the concept and content of representation in court. Solving these problems will improve the quality of our national legislation, minimize errors and shortcomings in the implementation of the law, and enhance the role of the institution of representation in court in ensuring the rights and freedoms of individuals. This, in turn, shows that the study of problems associated with the institution of representation in civil litigation based on civil procedural legal relations is extremely relevant for civil procedural law.

The list of used literature:

1. iDecree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" // National database of legislative information, 29.01.2022, No. 06/22/60/0082
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3. iConstitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 30.04.2023 // National database of legislative information, 01.05.2023, No. 03/23/837/0241
3. i<https://stat.sud.uz/file/2024/31.01/сайт%20фукаролик%202023%20йилик.pdf>